

FEATURES OF COMORBID DISORDERS IN PRIMARY HEADACHES

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Introduction. Sleep disturbances after primary headaches are a common complaint of patients seeking medical attention and are therefore of interest to many researchers. Although episodic forms of headache are not considered a serious medical or social problem, Primary headaches disrupt the patient's daily activities and quality of life and are accompanied by various concomitant disorders - depression, sleep disorders, somatoform disorders.

The purpose of the study. To study the features of comorbid disorders in primary headaches.

Materials and methods of research. The study examined data from 90 patients with comorbid disorders in primary headache. The patients underwent an objective clinical and neurological examination according to the standard scheme with an in-depth study of the neurological system. Patients are divided into 2 groups depending on gender

Results. The manifestation of comorbid disorders was studied in research groups. Emotional disturbances in patients with Group 1 were $55.56 \pm 5.86\%$ pre-treatment, and sleep disturbances were $90.28 \pm 3.49\%$. Emotional disorders in patients with Group 2 accounted for $68.89 \pm 6.9\%$ of pre-treatment cases and sleep disorders $57.78 \pm 7.36\%$.

Conclusion. Thus, while sleep disorders predominate over concomitant disorders in patients with primary headaches, emotional disorders predominate over frequent episodic tension headaches.